

Dealing with culture clashes

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Culture is a people's way of life. It can also be defined as a set of traditions adopted by certain groups of people. When we define culture, we have to talk about the cultural values, which are the principles, or qualities that a group of people will tend to view as good or right (Peterson22) .Different people from parts of the world have different ways of life. Some carry on activities not carried out by other people elsewhere.

The culture of people includes the food they eat, dances their race, their way of dressing, and religion just to mentions but a few. (Peterson 17) However, violent activities part of people's way of life.

That is, crime and criminal activities cannot be termed as part of people's culture. The Culture of people can remain the same or change with time, especially as people become more civilized. The change can also arise because of a prolonged exposure to a different culture. The exposure to these different cultures can result to positive or negative changes.(Haggis and Susanne18)

To some people, an activity carried out by others is not right before them.

For example, different groups of people have different modes of dressing especially for women. Some religions do not allow the exposure of some parts of the woman's body like the hair and the legs, while according to others it is very

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One example of a culture-clashing event is in the issue abortion. Abortion is the termination of pregnancy. Various circumstances force women to decide to have an abortion. Most of the times, cases of abortion are based on unwanted pregnancies. The only exception is when a woman is willing to have a child but due to health complications, the doctors advise on an abortion (Keown 99).

Others proceed with it because they cannot afford to have children mainly because they are not prepared in terms of finances. They do not want to fail in giving their children quality life or maybe they do not want to strain in the process of bringing up the child.

Getting a child out of wedlock is also a taboo to some people, and executing it can put one in social dilemma. Therefore, many prefer to do away with the pregnancy. From their parents. In other cases, their parents other them to do it. Other reasons for abortions include the need to continue with education or being in a demanding career. There has been a big conflict between pro-life pro-choice supporters especially in the United States of America where abortion has been legalized. Pro-life supporters do not advocate for abortion while the pro-life supporters believe that it is a woman's choice. Most of the pro-life supporters are mainly religious people.

Some countries have legalized abortion, which has led to a very big debate in the whole world, regarding its authorization. The issue has brought about a great conflict between these two groups of people. According to the religious people, abortion is a sin because it is termed as killing (Keown 20)

This is because they believe that life begins after conception and not birth. Once a woman becomes pregnant, she carries a life in her womb, which deserves due respect. According to them, it undermines human dignity because it deprives a

